

INCREASING THE EMPLOYMENT OF LABOR RESOURCES IN THE
AGRICULTURAL NETWORK

Norqabilov N. N. - Termiz State University, doctor of philosophy in economical science

Mamatkulov A. - Master student of Temiz State University.

Abstract: In this article, the specific features of increasing the employment of labor resources, the specific positive qualities of these subjects in the current globalization and information age, proposals for increasing the socio-economic well-being of the population employment have been developed.

Аннотация: В данной статье разработаны особенности повышения занятости трудовых ресурсов, конкретные положительные качества этих субъектов в современную глобализационно-информационную эпоху, а также предложения по повышению социально-экономического благосостояния населения.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mehnat resurslari bandligini oshirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari, hozirgi globallashuv va axborotlashgan davrda mazkur subyektlarning o'ziga xos ijobiy sifatleri, aholini band etish ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy farovonligini oshirish bo'yicha takliflar ishlab chiqilgan.

Key words: Economic growth, employment, efficiency, entrepreneurship, market infrastructure, prosperity, service.

Ключевы слова Экономический рост, занятость, эффективность, предпринимательство, рыночная инфраструктура, процветание, сервис.

Kalit so'zlar: iqtisodiy o'sish, bandlik, samaradorlik, tadbirkorlik, bozor infratuzilmasi, farovonlik, servis.

INTRODUCTION.

Further development of private sectors in rural areas is important in deepening and improving market reforms in our country. Without developing this sector of the economy, it is impossible to ensure the sustainable development of the country's economy, because agriculture is considered one of the real sectors of the economy, it provides raw materials for the industry, supplies food for the population, in addition to labor resources. More than 60 percent is accounted for by agriculture. The majority of unorganized youth and the volume of their foreign migration are in rural areas. Therefore, ensuring the employment of labor resources in rural areas requires the development of small business and private entrepreneurship.

In the following years, in our country, we introduced a procedure for allocating land plots that is equal for all, transparent and based on market principles, ensuring stability in property and legal relations related to land, protecting land, guaranteeing the property rights of land owners, as well as making it a civil law by determining the economic value of land. consistent reforms are being carried out to introduce it into free circulation as an object of relations.

At the same time, the procedure for conducting electronic online auctions has been developed for determining the lease of agricultural land plots through electronic online auctions.

In terms of job creation, 5,440 projects and 250,000 jobs will be created in the industrial sectors during 2023, 55,800 jobs in 8,430 projects in agriculture, and 11,000 projects in the service

sector 79 It is decided to strengthen the activity of regional, district and city governments to create 5,000 jobs.

In order to radically improve the situation in the remote districts of our republic, where the level of unemployment and demand in the labor market is high, the implementation of the mentioned measures was reflected in the strategy of actions. It is planned to create 56,800 jobs in 34 districts of our republic, where the unemployment rate is high and the situation in the labor market is difficult. Including: 15 thousand in industry; 9.7 thousand in the field of service and service; 15,500 under construction; 17,500 jobs will be created in agriculture, and this will be of great practical importance in ensuring the employment of the population.

The main part of labor resources in our republic lives in rural areas. So therefore, in order to improve the standard of living of the population, it is necessary to increase the number of small business entities in rural areas. It is necessary to increase the income of rural residents by modernizing the service and household sectors in rural areas. In our country, significant work has been carried out on the sustainable development of small business and private entrepreneurship, services and household industries, which ultimately have a significant impact on the improvement of the living standards of the rural population.

- in the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, the following should be done:

- increase of retail trade, catering, household service facilities in rural areas;
 - establishment of mini-banks in rural areas according to population;
 - opening information-resource centers in rural settlements (electronic libraries, centers connected to the Internet);
 - modernization of small enterprises, further acceleration of technical and technological re-equipment meeting the requirements of the present time, widespread introduction of modern, flexible and world-competitive technologies;
 - production of fruits and vegetables, packaging services, production of raw materials for packaging, organization of agricultural warehouses;
 - to increase the competitiveness of small enterprises by introducing a system of strict savings in the field of small business and private entrepreneurship, encouraging the reduction of production costs and product costs;
 - in order to finance programs aimed at increasing the income of low-income families, to ensure the employment of unemployed people, self-management bodies of labor and citizens, the Youth Union of Uzbekistan, the Women's Committee of Uzbekistan, other interested ministries and agencies strengthen cooperation with;
 - providing employment and increasing income of the population, especially in rural areas projects financing, new the work seats organize
- doing enterprises activities financial support, that's it including to them technological equipment and modernization for modern equipment and mini-technologies purchase to do loans to give
- our country of enterprises international in the market commodity and services level and quality increase and that's it basically commodity and services export increase.

Summary by doing that's it to say maybe village in places private sector more development through population the work with employment to increase and marriage degree it is possible to

make a great contribution to improvement , in general , to the improvement of infrastructure in our villages.

REFERENCES:

Norqobilov, N. (2020). The role of foreign investment in the development of the economy of Kashkadarya region. *Business Expert, 1*, 145.

Norqobilov, N., & Abdullayev, J. (2023). Specific features of solving the housing problem in our country in the context of economic reforms. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3*(2), 21-23.

Norkobilov , N. N. (2017). Education system from the budget except financing and personnel in preparation of marketing instead of *Contemporary education (Uzbekistan)* , (8), 36-40.

Norqobilov, N., & Rasulov, F. (2023). THE ROLE OF SOCIAL PROTECTION IN IMPROVING THE LIVING WELL-BEING OF THE POPULATION. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3*(2), 24-25.

Norkobilov, N. N. (2021). Structure and features of expanding investment in the southern region of uzbekistan. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities, 11*(11), 704-709.